
**Full mapping of the chain
process for three main
productions in EU**

JRP6 - NOVA - FBZ1 - 1st Call

NOVA D3.1

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Full mapping of the chain process for three main productions in E.U

Introduction

Syndromic surveillance (SyS) consists in the real-time collection, analysis, interpretation and diffusion of non-specific indicators in order to detect early any changes in human or animal health. SyS systems are expected to be earlier and more cost effective than traditional surveillance systems, since they make use of already existing data, collected at early steps of the disease continuum. This could include for instance over the count medicine sales, or even web-browser search queries, all of which are timelier than traditional surveillance based on laboratorial confirmation of diseases. However, because the data sources are also very unspecific, SyS is usually used in complement to traditional public health surveillance systems. Traditional surveillance, based on disease reporting, is often called « indicator-based » surveillance, while digital and syndromic surveillance, based on secondary data, is called « event-based » surveillance.

In their report laying out the strategic objectives and priorities for 2018-2020, the European Center for Disease Control (ECDC) supports the use of event-based and indicator-based surveillance in a systematic and complementary way, stating that « this will bring surveillance and epidemic intelligence closer together » (ECDC, 2018).

A survey of all syndromic surveillance systems in use in Europe (Dupuy et al. 2013) showed, in 2012, the existence of 22 active syndromic surveillance systems in public health, and 12 active systems in animal health, plus 11 and 15 pilots in each sector, respectively. Gastrointestinal illnesses were cited as one of the most frequent syndromes monitored, however there is no documentation that supports the existence of « one health » systems, which gather and analyse data across more than one sector in the same system (for instance animal and public health).

Foodborne (FBD) pathogens offer a good opportunity to design and pilot syndromic surveillance systems that combine health indicators across health sectors – here we refer to animal health, public health, and food surveillance – towards a framework of One-Health surveillance. Explicitly taking into consideration the synergies between the health of animals and humans, and exploring, when possible, data from food surveillance, is expected to improve timeliness and sensitivity of detection in public health surveillance. It is also expected to allow a shift from detection to prevention, as health indicators in animal health can be used to alert disease risks early, and prevent dissemination of pathogens to humans through food.

NOVA's WP3 was therefore designed to assess whether SyS in animal and food sectors could be a valuable add-on to the current or future surveillance of FBD in humans. The expected impacts are a better understanding of the interplay between animal and human health and an improvement of the prediction of human FBD outbreaks.

A first task to achieve this goal is the identification of opportunities for SyS across the food-chain. We believe that this should be achieved by two complementary tasks: 1) a detailed mapping of the food chain, in order to draw the background structure, over which syndromic surveillance systems could be implemented; and 2) a detailed inventory of data sources existing along this food producing continuum, accompanied of a critical assessment of the potential of these data for use in SyS.

This report documents our progress towards the first step.

Food chain mapping

We planned to draw a comprehensive map of the food chain, from primary production to human consumption, for at least 3 examples. These examples would, ideally, come from different countries, and be based on different animal sectors (cattle, pig and poultry).

The food chain mapping was achieved through three stages of information collection:

- 1) Draw all actors and events in the chain, in order to identify the players and the opportunities for hazard propagation.
- 2) Identify events generating health indicators data: data regarding the detection of a hazard, indirect indicators of hazard presence, or risk indicators.
- 3) Identify existing data sources in this continuum.

Figures 1 to 3 below present the results of the steps outlined above for the first full mapping completed, the food chain of poultry production and consumption in France.

Upon finalizing this mapping, we identified strong synergies with other WPs, within different projects in the EJP group of projects. In particular, the work being developed in WP1 in NOVA, and WP1 in ORION. Therefore, we deemed very relevant to subject our first food chain mapping to their review and input, before proceeding to the mapping of cattle and pig production and consumption chains. While it is still the goal of this WP to produce 2 more food chain mappings, we believe that at this stage it is more relevant to make sure that we are harmonised with other groups developing similar work, so that the outputs of all projects can be compatible, and therefore have higher adoptability. **We will produce an updated version of this report, with two further mappings, and with documented synergies with parallel WPs, by M12.**

References

- Dupuy, Céline, Anne Bronner, Eamon Watson, Linda Wuyckhuise-Sjouke, Martin Reist, Anne Fouillet, Didier Calavas, Pascal Hendriks, and Jean-Baptiste Perrin. 2013. "Inventory of Veterinary Syndromic Surveillance Initiatives in Europe (Triple-S Project): Current Situation and Perspectives." *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 111 (3). Elsevier B.V.: 220–29. View also a short version of the inventory at : <http://invs.santepubliquefrance.fr/Dossiers-thematiques/Veille-et-alerte/Projet-Triple-S/Triple-S-the-syndromic-surveillance-project>
- ECDC (European Center for Disease Control). 2018. "Single Programming Document - 2018-2020.", Draft. Available at <https://ecdc.europa.eu/sites/portal/files/documents/ECDC-Single-Programming-Document-2018.pdf>.

Figure 1. Food chain of poultry production and consumption in France: actors and events.

Figure 2. Food chain of poultry production and consumption in France; complemented with a mapping of the events producing data potentially useful for surveillance.

Figure 3. Food chain of poultry production and consumption in France; complemented with a mapping of the events producing data potentially useful for surveillance, as well as the existing data sources identified.

